

CLINICAL EFFICACY OF BACTERIOPHAGE "SECTAFAGE" IN SCARLET FEVER IN CHILDREN

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Introduction. Characteristic of streptococcal infection is the change of circulating strains of the pathogen with a predominance of highly virulent variants. There is a tendency to aggravate the clinic and increase the frequency of complications after the disease.

Purpose of the study: Evaluation of the clinical efficacy of the bacteriophage "Sextaphage" in the treatment of children with Scarlet fever.

Material and methods. The study was conducted in the City Clinical Infectious Diseases Hospital №1, in the period May-July 2022. The study included 68 children, aged 2-13 years, who were in the children's department with a diagnosis of «Scarlet fever. Medium severity». The children were divided into 2 groups, where the first - the main group consisted of children, in the amount of 38, who, along with the conventional treatment (CT), took the drug "Sextafag". The average age of the children was 5.39 ± 0.37 years. The second - control group included 30 children who received CT, the average age in this group was 5.75 ± 0.80 years. Boys predominated in the main and control groups, 60.5% and 66.7%, respectively. The groups were comparable in terms of gender and age. The CT included etiotropic (benzylpenicillin or azithromycin), pathogenetic (glucose-saline solution, desensitizing solutions), symptomatic (paracetamol or ibuprofen) therapy. A conversation was held with the parents of the children, information about the drug was provided, consent was obtained from the parents to participate in the study, and an informed consent sheet was signed. When evaluating the effectiveness of therapy, the length of stay in the hospital, the persistence of patient complaints, and the dynamics of the clinical manifestations of Scarlet fever were considered.

Results and discussion. The analysis showed that the duration of inpatient treatment of patients in the main group averaged 5.16 ± 0.06 days (minimum 4, maximum 6 days), in the control group - 8.25 ± 0.57 days (min 7, max 14 days). The duration of general weakness in the main group was 3.92 ± 0.14 days, significantly different from the average value in the control group (5.08 ± 0.10) ($p < 0.05$). Lethargy, in both groups, was almost the same (26.32 ± 0.83 and 25.0 ± 1.44 , respectively), but had a different duration in these studied groups,

but was significantly longer observed in patients in the second group and amounted to $2,63 \pm 0.11$ and 4.0 ± 0.14 days, respectively. A rash on the body in the main group was observed in 94.74 ± 1.57 and 91.67 ± 2.75 of cases, while the duration of rash detection in the main and control groups was 3.89 ± 0.12 and 4.75 ± 0.10 , respectively, significantly different from each other ($p < 0.05$). The same characteristic picture took place in the duration of such symptoms as sore throat (3.84 ± 0.12 and 4.50 ± 0.11 days, respectively), throat hyperemia (3.03 ± 0.12 and 3.92 ± 0.13 days, respectively). The duration of the febrile period in patients in the main group was 3.74 ± 0.12 days, in the control group this symptom was significantly longer (4.33 ± 0.11 days). Also, for a longer time in the control group, an increase in lymph nodes (3.67 ± 0.11 days) and palatine tonsils (4.58 ± 0.12 days) was observed, with their duration in the main group 2.71 ± 0.11 and $4,03 \pm 0.12$ days, respectively ($p < 0.05$). The results of a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of the bacteriophage "Sextaphage" based on the study of the duration of the main clinical symptoms in the group of patients with the inclusion of bacteriophage in the CT (main group) and the group of patients with only CT (control group) showed a reduction in hospital bed days due to a significant reduction the duration of such manifestations of the disease as general weakness, lethargy, sore throat, hyperemia of the throat, swollen lymph nodes and palatine tonsils in sick children in the main group.

Conclusion. Thus, the study and the results obtained allow us to recommend the use of the bacteriophage Sextaphage in complex therapy in children with a moderate form of streptococcal infection.

